

Burnout and Organisational Citizenship Behaviour among Health Sciences Faculty: Evidence from Colombia and Ecuador

Diego Alonso Peña¹

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4390-0896>

***Braian López Ossa**²

<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-9381-000X>

Karol Johanna Briñez Ariza³

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0595-1716>

Pablo Vicente Bravo Lozano⁴

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8891-7806>

^{1,3}Fundación Universitaria del Área Andina – Pereira Campus, Faculty of Health and Sports Sciences, Nursing Research Group of Risaralda (GIER)

²Universidad Católica de Manizales, Faculty of Health Sciences
Manizales, Caldas, Colombia

⁴Universidad Técnica Particular de Loja- Loja Ecuador, Health Faculty

*²Corresponding author, email: blopez@ucm.edu.co

Abstract

Background: Higher education faculty frequently experience significant stress due to the demanding nature of academic life. While the impact of Burnout Syndrome (BS) on teacher health is well documented, the specific relationship between BS and Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) remains underexplored, particularly within the health sciences.

Objective: This study aims to analyse the relationship between burnout dimensions and organisational citizenship behaviour among health science professors in Colombia and Ecuador.

Methodology: A quantitative, correlational, and cross-sectional study was conducted using probabilistic sampling. The final sample consisted of 113 participants. Data were collected using the Maslach Burnout Inventory and the Scale of Organisational Citizenship Behaviour among Co-workers (ECCOCT). Statistical analysis, including descriptive and correlational assessments, was performed using Just Another Statistical Program (JASP).

Results: Findings reveal notable levels of emotional exhaustion and depersonalisation, indicative of burnout. However, most participants maintained a positive perception of their professional efficacy and job satisfaction. Correlational analysis indicates that emotional exhaustion and depersonalisation negatively affect OCB, suggesting that increased burnout levels significantly decrease discretionary work behaviours.

Unique Contribution: This research provides rare empirical evidence on the correlation between burnout and OCB, specifically among health sciences faculty in a South American context, offering critical insights into how emotional exhaustion hampers institutional cohesion.

Conclusion: The work behaviours of health sciences professors are significantly impacted by burnout, even when professional efficacy remains stable. These results highlight the intricate link between organisational dynamics and educator well-being.

Key Recommendation: Institutions should implement occupational health programmes and mental health interventions that focus on protective factors. Mentoring sessions and the development of formal institutional health policies are essential for mitigating burnout and sustaining positive organisational behaviours.

Keywords: health sciences, burnout, faculty, organisational culture, nursing, OCB.

Introduction

Work exhaustion is a phenomenon of interest that affects mental health. Burnout syndrome is understood as a state of distress that occurs between a person's being and their work. Maslach described it in terms of three domains: diminished personal fulfilment, emotional and/or physical exhaustion, and depersonalisation (a distant attitude towards people and the work environment) (Baka et al., 2025). There is a close relationship between emotional exhaustion and organisational citizenship behaviour. Exhaustion significantly reduces empathy and motivation, which are related to the initiative to engage in prosocial and cooperative behaviour. This translates into a progressive impact on emotional well-being, commitment, and organisational climate in the area of health education.

Consequently, teachers in higher education programmes in health-related areas are exposed to frequent stress and have been found to have high levels of emotional exhaustion, which is the first indicator of burnout syndrome. Therefore, the need to investigate this and intervene preventively through organisational adjustments has been documented (Xavier et al., 2024). The other concept in this study is that of organisational citizenship behaviour, which refers to behavioural manifestations that affect performance and involve acts of courtesy, civic participation, altruism, and awareness (Rizaie et al., 2023).

The purpose of this research is to analyse the relationship between burnout and organisational citizenship behaviour among health science professors at three higher education institutions in Latin America.

Literature review and hypothesis development

The scientific literature on burnout and organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) among university professors, particularly in the social sciences, has shown sustained growth over the

last decade (2015-2025). A review of English-language publications reveals a robust body of knowledge addressing both the psychosocial dynamics associated with burnout syndrome and the prosocial behaviours that emerge among co-workers. This background provides a solid theoretical foundation for the present research and confirms the phenomenon's relevance and validity. The search equation and number of articles are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Search equation in Scopus

Data base	Number of documents	Search equation
Scopus	22	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("burnout" OR "burn-out" OR "occupational burnout" OR "professional burnout") AND ("organizational citizenship behavior" OR "OCB" OR "citizenship behavior" OR "extra-role behavior" OR "comportamiento organizacional") AND ("teachers" OR "faculty" OR "universit y teachers" OR "higher education professors" OR "academic staff" OR "docentes" OR "profesores universitarios")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English"))

Note. Final equation in the Scopus database after cleaning.

After searching the database, a bibliometric analysis of scientific output on this topic was carried out, visualised using term co-occurrence networks in the VOSviewer software created by Romano (2018), revealing a semantic structure organised into clearly differentiated thematic clusters. The identification of these conceptual clusters allows us to define the main lines of research and the gaps in the literature. This organisation of the academic field reinforces the study's theoretical basis and validates the relevance of the adopted conceptual framework.

Figure 1: Bibliometric networks

Note. Created using VOSviewer software.

Figure 1 identifies two main clusters in the literature on burnout and organisational citizenship behaviour in teachers. The first cluster groups together studies that examine the relationship between burnout and OCB in teachers, highlighting how exhaustion influences prosocial

behaviour among colleagues. The second cluster focuses on the association between job satisfaction and burnout, understanding satisfaction as a relevant factor in teacher well-being. Together, these clusters highlight the two predominant research paths and support the relevance of the approach adopted in the present study. Prior research has shown a negative correlation between overall burnout and organisational citizenship behaviour. However, there is insufficient data to distinguish the effects of each burnout syndrome dimension, exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal accomplishment, on organisational citizenship behaviours, which is the main goal of this study.

Burnout Syndrome

The history of burnout syndrome dates back to 1974, when psychiatrist Herbert J. Freudenberger observed that most volunteers at a drug addiction clinic in New York, after a year of work, experienced a progressive loss of energy that led to exhaustion, accompanied by symptoms of anxiety and depression, as well as job demotivation and aggression towards patients. Based on these findings, he defined burnout syndrome as a feeling of failure, exhaustion or depletion resulting from excessive demands on energy, strength or resources.

The concept of burnout was formally introduced into medical literature at that time. In the 1980s, psychologist Christina Maslach of the University of California, Berkeley, revived the term used by Freudenberger to define burnout syndrome (Maslach Jackson, 1982). This concept was reformulated by Maslach and Jackson in 1981, who described it as an inadequate way of coping with chronic emotional stress, characterised by emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation and reduced personal fulfilment (Akman et al., 2016).

With reference to Blau's social exchange theory (1964), emotional exhaustion significantly affects civic engagement, reducing psychological resources and coping strategies, which leads to a perception that institutional demands require additional effort, leading to minimal, sole and exclusive fulfilment of acquired commitments, minimising prosocial behaviours and involvement in institutional activities, in turn affecting collaborative work, aspects that are of vital importance in health training.

Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB)

This refers to behavioural manifestations that affect performance and include acts of courtesy, civic participation, altruism, and conscientiousness (Rodríguez Montalbán et al., 2013). However, university teaching often has negative consequences due to the arduous responsibilities that arise daily, not only for oneself but also for students and other members of the educational community. Teachers must face vital challenges, one of the most significant being the constant maintenance of interpersonal relationships.

As pointed out by Alvarado Peña et al. (2023), the professional environment of university teachers poses psychosocial risks that lead to various work-related difficulties. Therefore, when teachers are unable to meet the objectives imposed by the profession or to create and maintain healthy relational bonds, this psychosocial risk extends to teachers, students, and the educational community as a whole, as it hinders the transmission and development of organisational skills. Finally, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H0: There is no significant relationship between emotional exhaustion and altruism in health science teachers.

H1: There is a significant relationship between emotional exhaustion and altruism in health science teachers.

H0: There is no significant relationship between emotional exhaustion and sportsmanship in health science teachers.

H1: There is a significant relationship between emotional exhaustion and sportsmanship in health science teachers.

H0: There is no significant relationship between depersonalisation and conscientiousness in health science teachers.

H1: There is a significant relationship between depersonalisation and conscientiousness in health science teachers.

H0: There is no significant relationship between personal fulfilment and civic engagement in health science teachers.

H1: There is a significant relationship between personal fulfilment and civic engagement in health science teachers.

Methodology

This research was conducted using a quantitative approach, with a descriptive observational design and a correlational scope. This type of study allows for the examination of the degree of association between two or more variables, as each is measured independently and the relationships between them are subsequently analysed using correlation techniques (Hernández, 2014).

Study population: A total of 279 professors from two universities in western Colombia and one in southern Ecuador.

Sample

A probabilistic sample calculation was performed with a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 5%, resulting in a sample of 163 professors representing the universe, of whom 113 responded to the call.

Inclusion criteria

Undergraduate health sciences professors who voluntarily agreed to respond to the research instruments and format.

Exclusion criteria

Professors who had been with the institution for less than one year, who were hired on a service contract basis, who worked part-time, who had other external employment, and who were training professors.

Study variable

An independent variable, which is burnout, and a dependent variable, which is the organisational citizenship behaviour of employees.

Information collection

The information was collected in higher education institutions during the months of May to July 2025. Before carrying out this phase, it was necessary to request authorisation from the ethics committee of one of the higher education institutions. After approval was granted, the deans' offices were informed so that the instrument could be sent via an online questionnaire.

Instruments

Maslach Burnout Questionnaire

This is a self-administered instrument that assesses chronic stress in teachers (Maslach et al., 2015). It has been validated in Spanish by several authors (Jiménez-Padilla et al., 2023). It has 22 items and three dimensions (emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation, personal fulfilment)

and six response options (never, once a week, once a month or less, several times a week, several times a month, once a year or less).

Work colleague Organisational Citizenship Behaviour Scale (Eccoct)

Validated for Latin American Spanish (Ossa et al., 2025). It has five dimensions (altruism, courtesy, civic conscientiousness, sportsmanship, and conscientiousness). It has 15 items and 6 response options on a Likert scale: Strongly disagree, Partially disagree, Slightly disagree, Slightly agree, Partially agree, Strongly agree.

Reliability of the instruments

The reliability of the instruments was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, with the following results: the burnout instrument had a coefficient of 0.686, although acceptable reliability may be low for the threshold stipulated in scientific evidence; however, it cannot be said that the sample is a limiting factor, since in the study conducted by (Aranda Beltrán et al., 2016) with a sample of 1,958 workers, a reliability of (0.658) was obtained for the entire scale, which is therefore within the normal range, while the organisational citizenship behaviour scale among co-workers reached (0.939). These values demonstrate adequate internal consistency of the instruments used in the study (Oviedo & Campo-Arias, 2005).

Data analysis method

Statistical analysis was performed using open-access JASP version 0.19.1 (An open-source, free statistical analysis program funded by the University of Amsterdam).

Results

The study covered a sample of 113 taxpayers, of whom 69.91% were women and 30.09% were men. Most were in the 40-49 age range (37.17%), followed by the 30-39 age group (23.89%), indicating a working-age midlife population.

In terms of marital status, the married group predominated (50.44%), followed by single people (34.51%). In terms of educational level, a high level of qualification was evident: 73.45% had a master's degree, and 22.12% had a university specialisation. Regarding length of service at the university, the highest percentage (27.43%) was among those who had been there for 11 to 15 years, while total time in the profession showed a higher concentration in the 11 to 20-year range (36.28%). Finally, 53.98% of participants had permanent contracts, and 46.02% had fixed-term contracts, reflecting a relatively balanced distribution in terms of job stability.

With the aim of investigating whether gender, educational level, and nationality act as moderating variables in the relationship between emotional exhaustion and organisational citizenship behaviour, a multigroup analysis was carried out using Spearman's correlation coefficients (ρ). This strategy was adopted, considering the ordinal nature of the scales used and the absence of normality assumptions, and allowed us to verify the dimensionality and significance of the associations between sociodemographic subgroups without fitting more restrictive parametric models.

In accordance with the above, when the analysis was performed by gender, it was observed that in women the correlation was practically nil ($\rho = 0.01$; $p = 0.90$), while in men a very low negative association was identified ($\rho = -0.12$; $p = 0.49$). However, these descriptive

differences indicate a slightly more negative trend in the male group, none of the correlations achieved statistical significance, which rules out a moderating effect of gender.

Similarly, the analysis by educational level did not show a statistically significant difference. The correlations between burnout and organisational citizenship were not significant at any of the levels analysed, with only a moderate negative trend in the group of university specialists ($\rho = -0.33$; $p = 0.09$), which did not exceed the significance threshold and should be interpreted with caution. At the other educational levels, the associations were weak, which prevents us from maintaining a consistent moderating effect of educational level.

Finally, when considering nationality, the results showed a positive relationship of very high magnitude and statistically significant in both Colombian ($\rho = 0.97$; $p < 0.001$) and Ecuadorian ($\rho = 0.98$; $p < 0.001$) participants. However, the near-absolute similarity in the magnitude of the coefficients between the two groups indicates that nationality does not introduce substantial variation in the relationship analysed, so there is no evidence of a moderating effect attributable to country of origin. For future purposes, it would be interesting to analyse the context at the Latin American level.

Relationship between burnout and organisational citizenship behaviour

Given that the data did not follow a normal distribution, as verified by a Q-Q plot and the Shapiro-Wilk test, it was decided to apply Spearman's rank correlation test (Mendivelso, 2022).

Table 2: *Relationship between Burnout and ECCOCT*

Burnout Dimension	Burnout Item	ECCOCT Dimension	Item ECCOCT	Spearman rho	p-value	Interpretation
Emotional Exhaustion	I1P1	Altruism	I2P1	-0.236*	0.012	Greater burnout means less help from peers.
	I1P6	Altruism	I2P1	-0.316*	<.001	Greater work stress less cooperation.
	I1P1	Civic Engagement	I2P8	-0.384*	<.001	Greater exhaustion leads to less organisational commitment.
	I1P6	Sportsmanship	I2P10	-0.345*	<.001	Greater burnout leads to less work resilience.
	I1P14	Awareness	I2P4	-0.316*	<.001	Greater exhaustion leads to less compliance with regulations.
Depersonalization	I1P5	Civic Engagement	I2P7	-0.288*	0.002	Greater cynicism less institutional pride.
	I1P15	Awareness	I2P5	-0.215*	0.022	Greater cynicism less responsibility.
	I1P12	Altruism	I2P1	0.321*	<.001	Greater vitality greater altruism.

Personal Accomplishment	I1P19:	Civic Engagement	I2P9	0.439*	<.001	Greater job satisfaction, greater commitment.
	I1P12	Sportsmanship	I2P12	0.395*	<.001	Greater vitality greater perseverance.
	I1P4	Politeness	I2P13	0.199*	0.035	Greater understanding greater proactive communication.

Note. Prepared internally. Correlation analysis was performed using JASP software.

Table 2 shows that emotional exhaustion and depersonalisation (dimensions of burnout) have a negative impact on work behaviours. The greater the exhaustion, the lower the altruism ($\rho = -0.236^*$ to -0.316^*), Civic Engagement ($\rho = -0.384^*$), Sportsmanship ($\rho = -0.345^*$) and Conscientiousness ($\rho = -0.316^*$), suggesting that work stress reduces cooperation, resilience and responsibility. Similarly, cynicism (depersonalisation) is associated with lower Civic Participation ($\rho = -0.288^*$) and Conscientiousness ($\rho = -0.215$), reflecting negative attitudes towards work. Depersonalisation or cynicism, linked to low accountability, progressively deteriorates the functional educational bond, affects learning outcomes related to shortcomings in tutoring and academic support, and diminishes institutional identity.

Figure 2: Positive effect of personal fulfilment versus the negative effect of exhaustion on organisational citizenship behaviour

Note. Own elaboration. Figure 2 shows a negative correlation ($\rho = -0.38$) between personal fulfilment and emotional exhaustion, demonstrating that greater emotional exhaustion leads to lower personal fulfilment.

In Figure 2, personal fulfilment showed the opposite effect: employees with greater job satisfaction and vitality tend to develop greater altruism ($\rho = 0.321^*$), Civic Participation ($\rho = 0.439^*$) and Sportsmanship ($\rho = 0.395^*$). In addition, those who had a greater understanding showed Courtesy ($\rho = 0.199^*$). These effects emphasise that well-being at

work not only reduces burnout but also encourages positive behaviour, improving the organisational climate.

In accordance with the above, it can be stated that the correlations observed are weak, according to the Spearman correlation interpretation scale proposed by Cabrera (2009). It should be noted that all dimensions presented both positive and negative correlations.

However, there is evidence of a $P (< .005)$ and weak significance (*) in all dimensions, so the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted, which would suggest that:

1. H1: There is a significant relationship between emotional exhaustion and altruism in health science teachers.
2. H1: There is a significant relationship between emotional exhaustion and sportsmanship in health science teachers.
3. H1: There is a significant relationship between depersonalisation and conscientiousness in health science teachers.
4. H1: There is a significant relationship between personal fulfilment and civic participation in health science teachers.

A significant limitation of the study relates to the sample's response rate. Although the probability calculation specified a sample of 163 teachers with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, only 113 teachers responded to the call; this may limit the generalisation of the findings to the entire population, as well as introducing a possible non-response bias associated with the differences in characteristics between those who participated and those who did not.

Discussion

The results obtained showed that the phenomenon under study presents levels of emotional exhaustion and depersonalisation indicative of burnout among teachers in Colombia and Ecuador who are actively employed in mid-life and who maintain positive perceptions and behaviours of organisational citizenship among their colleagues. However, both emotional exhaustion and depersonalisation could negatively affect organisational citizenship behaviours in the future, leading to greater burnout.

In line with the above, the dimension of sportsmanship takes on a particularly sensitive meaning within the academic environment. The significant negative correlation between exhaustion and sportsmanship ($\rho = -0.345^*$) indicates that, when emotional exhaustion is prolonged, teachers find it increasingly difficult to maintain a tolerant attitude towards the periodic difficulties of university work. Chronic stress not only depletes energy but also slowly deteriorates the ability to understand mistakes, accept adversity, and maintain a productive attitude towards institutional requirements. In this scenario, so-called work resilience is progressively enveloped by a negative effect.

In the present study, teachers with service or part-time contracts were excluded, as the results differ for them because there is less possibility of developing emotional exhaustion due to low exposure to work demands, as their contracts are limited to the fulfilment of specific tasks, thus strengthening autonomy, time management and the perception of self-control due to the absence of additional demands, which leads to less institutional involvement.

According to these results, other recent publications also report that university teachers experience emotional exhaustion. In a sample of 410 teachers in Thailand, 234 of them were found to have medium to high levels of emotional exhaustion (Pakdee et al., 2025). This indicates that, in other contexts, fatigue and low energy significantly permeate teaching work and can compromise physical and emotional health and performance over time.

For university lecturers, there are situations that exacerbate exhaustion, such as work pressures, heavy academic workloads, and high stress from performance evaluations, emphasising the need for high efficiency amid great responsibilities. According to the study by Sha et al., a negative correlation was found between burnout syndrome and work performance (Sha & Chang, 2025). There are theoretical proposals, such as resource conservation, that suggest teachers with adequate resources in the workplace could manage stress more easily and comfortably. Some resources could include psychological support, opportunities for openness about assigned tasks, and an environment conducive to mental and physical well-being.

Qualitative evidence from university teachers revealed expressions of appreciation for supportive relationships in the work environment, although hierarchies also affect the exhaustion that results from high workloads (Li, 2025). This approach opens opportunities to effect changes in the structures of management and the development of university work environments. It should be noted that close relationships, support, and collective construction can probably improve well-being in the workplace, but adjustments are needed in the hierarchies present in universities.

Organisational Citizenship Behaviour

The dimensions of Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) – altruism, conscientiousness, civic participation, sportsmanship and courtesy – vary among individuals, demonstrating the diversity of voluntary behaviours beyond formal responsibilities. Previous studies indicate that factors such as work commitment and perceived organisational support influence altruistic and compliance behaviours related to altruism and conscientiousness (Mansour & Tremblay, 2018). In addition, professional competence contributes to job satisfaction, civic participation, and sportsmanship (Biagioli et al., 2018), while courtesy and interpersonal relationships are crucial for validating the ECCOCT scale (Rodríguez Montalbán et al., 2013). However, risk factors associated with teacher burnout can diminish these dimensions, highlighting the importance of prevention and comprehensive care strategies to reinforce a positive organisational climate. Taken together, these findings underscore that CCO is a key component of institutional cohesion and success.

Articulation with Betty Newman's Systems Model

In accordance with Betty Newman's nursing systems model, some central concepts from the model were selected to enable articulation with the study results and facilitate their understanding (Wang et al., 2020).

First, the teacher is conceived as the client system, in reciprocal interaction with the environment, which has a natural line of defence, a flexible line of defence, and lines of resistance that are activated for protection, preventing work stressors from crossing over and affecting the well-being of the client system (teacher). Second, stressors, according to the theory, are stimuli that produce tension within the limits of the client system, generating

positive or negative results. In this study, burnout syndrome is the result of the impact on the lines of resistance, which, according to the theory, has crossed the lines of defence and caused a negative response in the client system. Burnout can be seen as a stressor and a result that affects the teacher's homeostasis.

In this study, the response is organisational citizenship behaviour, where it was concluded that the presence of burnout has a significant impact on teachers' ability to participate in these citizenship behaviours. According to the above, based on Neuman's model, when the system's defence lines are breached by a stressor, the client system's energy is depleted, which manifests itself in a reduction in positive and productive behaviours, such as organisational citizenship behaviour. This research corroborates that burnout syndrome is a stressor that affects the client system, which, when not adequately addressed by institutions or by the client system itself, compromises and deteriorates the teacher's ability to maintain their well-being and be active and participatory in their work environment.

Although the study provides relevant evidence on the relationship between burnout and organisational citizenship behaviours, it is important to recognise several methodological limitations. First, the cross-sectional design used prevents the establishment of causal relationships between the variables analysed, as the information was obtained at a single point in time, making it impossible to determine the temporal direction of the observed effects. Furthermore, although a probabilistic sampling calculation was performed, the final sample consisted of 113 participants from a universe of 279 teachers, which not only reduces statistical power but also makes the sample a functional convenience sample, susceptible to non-response bias. This may limit the generalisation of the findings to the total population of health science teachers.

Additionally, the use of self-administered instruments introduces the risk of social desirability bias, as participants may respond in ways that project a favourable image of themselves or minimise negative experiences associated with burnout. This type of bias may underestimate the actual severity of symptoms or overestimate prosocial behaviours, affecting the accuracy of the correlations found. Taken together, these limitations should be considered when interpreting the results and proposing future research to deepen understanding of the phenomenon.

Conclusion

The findings demonstrate that burnout is a major stressor that affects organisational citizenship behaviours in health sciences teachers, particularly in the aspect of emotional weariness. Increased fatigue and depersonalization are linked to a decline in altruism, civic engagement, sportsmanship, and conscientiousness, notwithstanding the modest relationships found. Simultaneously, the sample's high level of personal fulfilment serves as a protective factor that boosts prosocial behaviours and fortifies the organisational climate. These results imply that institutional management of burnout is essential for both ensuring collaborative dynamics, which are essential to academic performance, and protecting teachers' well-being. Institutional management processes carried out by administrators and deans constitute a positive aspect of constant feedback, promoting faculty well-being and strengthening institutional commitment, improving the organisational climate and the fulfilment of established functions and goals. This strengthens communication and continuous improvement processes, academic results and satisfaction among faculty and students, as well as institutional pride.

The identified burnout profile, which is marked by high levels of emotional exhaustion and concurrently low levels of depersonalization and high levels of personal fulfilment, aligns with the "overloaded" pattern reported in recent literature. This suggests that the accumulation of work demands over time, rather than emotional detachment or feelings of ineffectiveness, is the root cause of burnout. When seen in the context of Betty Neuman's Systems Model, this arrangement demonstrates how work-related stressors have penetrated the teaching system's defences, lowering the energy available to implement constructive organisational behaviours. Thus, it is determined that the best therapies should concentrate on controlling workload, bolstering institutional defences, and encouraging organisational support techniques that maintain teachers' organisational citizenship behaviours and mental health.

Declarations

AI Use Statement: The authors confirm that no artificial intelligence tools were used in the drafting or production of this manuscript.

Data availability statement: The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, [Braian Lopez Ossa], upon reasonable request.

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Conflict of interest: The authors declare that they have no financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work presented in this article.

Ethical approval: This study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of The Catholic University of Manizales (Protocol Code [122] of June 2018).

Authors' contributions: D.A.P; B.L.O conceived and designed the study; D.A.P; B.L.O; K.J.B.A; P.V.B.L collected the data; D.A.P; B.L.O analysed the data; D.A.P; B.L.O; K.J.B.A; P.V.B.L drafted the article. All authors have read and approved the published version.

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